

Areas of improvement of public administration organizational arrangement of regional personnel policy formation

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Abstract. Topical issues of public administration of personnel policy formation are summarized in the article. Foreign experience of the public administration organizational arrangement of personnel policy formation is analyzed. Taking into account international practices, the main public administration areas of forming active personnel policy have been summed up. Key elements of regional personnel policy have been generalized. Ways of improvement of the public administration organizational arrangement of personnel policy formation have been offered.

1 Introduction

Under today's conditions of development of the state, one of the top-priority tasks is increasing its competitiveness. The mechanism of competitiveness is based on the efficient use of natural, industrial, technological, labor, financial and other resources. The availability of resources and the fullness of their mobilization give the state absolute and competitive advantages over other countries. The working-age population itself is a factor in the efficiency of functioning of enterprises and GDP volume growth, which determines the overall level of socio-economic development.

Important aspects of public administration in the field of human resources, including the problems of development of the organizational arrangement of public administration in the formation of personnel policy, and its functioning in market conditions, are researched by such scientists as L. Antonova, V. Beschastnyi, V. Biehlytsia, D. Dzvinchuk, S. Dombrovs'ka, M. Zgurovs'kyi, A. Kobets', V. Kovrehin, I. Lopushyns'kyi, S. Maistro, V. Oharenko, V. Sadkovyi, V. Sychenko, V. Shvedun, and others.

For several decades, Ukrainian labor market differed from the others in its distinguishing features and could be characterized, on the one hand, by high-rate capacity building, on the other hand, by a heap of inadequately employed. In Ukraine, for many years, mainly under the influence of ideological postulates, a cult of physical and, therefore, menial work has developed. These conditions have led to the formation of a unique type of employee - passive to the process of self-development and lacking initiative at work [1, p. 176].

20 November 2020

2 Presenting main material

In recent years, new organizational approaches to the public administration of the process of regional personnel policy formation have been needed. And the difficulties the regions have encountered are quite general, while the arrangement of overcoming difficulties, in particular, organizational and management systems are not sufficiently effective.

The complexity of the problems of public administration in the formation of personnel policy is caused by the following reasons:

- lap-sided growth of the economic base;
- deformation of socio-demographic structure;
- low level of municipal infrastructure.

Optimization of the state regulation system can be achieved only by complex solutions and the use of an integrated approach during the management formation (modeling).

When designing an effective management system, a conceptual model that adequately describes the totality of regional processes, first of all, interaction with the external environment is needed. Such a model can be based on the principles of systematic analysis, comprising economic and structural, dynamic and ideological aspects. The formation of such a model is methodologically determined by a systematic approach, and herewith those areas of information and operating bases are used that are crucial both in the system itself and in the external environment [2].

When forming an efficient personnel policy, the experience of countries-marketers should be taken into consideration. Official labor market management in western countries is performed at three levels: state, territorial and at enterprises. There are numerous models of management that differ by their target, methods, and funds, conditions of economic development.

The margins of the labor market government control are determined by many factors: the position of monopolies, small and medium-sized businesses, individual taxpayers, and the size of financial and other resources.

In most Western countries, central government bodies are dealing with employment and vocational training, and relevant laws governing employment processes. Countries such as Sweden and France are characterized by the government monopoly on employment issues. However, at all levels of government, there are so-called triple unions, which comprise representatives of government agencies, employers and trade unions, that offer a means for deeper learning of the requirements and claims to find the best solutions. In our country, this experience is codified by the Law of Ukraine "On Employment of the Population".

Conditionally, the practices of employment services in advanced economies, according to N. Medvedev, can be divided into two types, based upon the United States and Sweden [3].

The US-based employment system encourages an employee to get actively involved in the job search. It provides an employee with the necessary information about the situation on the labor market counseling during employment. This system eliminates the monopoly of the state employment service and gives them wide possibilities of free choice of employment. But in the 1990s there began a Swedish-style shift towards the active public policies on the issues of the labor market.

In Sweden, in the 1950s, the economic policy model was developed to achieve the goal of full employment without inflation. The model assumes a reduction in the overall

20 November 2020

demand for labor to the point where not all labor force is used. Besides, funds are used in case there are any employment problems. The policy aims at achieving prosperity through full employment and equal pay while maintaining market economy principles.

Active labor market policies can and must guarantee not specific types of work, but only general employment. Hence, the main term in the Swedish labor market policy is "mobility". Swedish employment services estimated that 3/4 out of the total expenditure on employment was used for active labor market policy, and only 1/4 was directed at unemployment benefits. These funds were generated mainly through tax payments. However, in Sweden, tax policy based on progressive rates and the use of a wage system led to a reduction in job motivation and the competitiveness of manufactured goods and promoted a passive culture of dependency. The unemployed, receiving substantial benefits and being able to live at the expense of society, were most often not motivated to look for work. All these negative consequences made Swedish authorities revise some of the postulates of personnel policy.

In recent years, Ukraine has set the course towards the active personnel policy in the labor market. Due regard should, however, be paid to the negative consequences of pursuing the above mentioned policies of foreign countries.

Given the world experience, the main directions of public administration in the process of forming active personnel policy should include:

- vocational and additional training, career-guidance and incentivizing adaptation to the situation on the labor market;
- encouraging the unemployed to actively seek job and entrepreneurs to increase employment by providing them with subsidies and tax perks;
- creating conditions for entrepreneurs to hire certain groups of unemployed people (young people, people with disabilities, long-term unemployed).

Moreover, the focus of the implementation of socio-economic policy, and in particular personnel policy, is now shifting to the regions. It is in the regions where the problems of livelihood, reproduction, and employment of the population are solved. Regional organs of governments are primarily responsible to the population and the state for the situation in the region. This is the essence of decentralization of management - to transfer a large part of rights and the corresponding share of responsibilities to the local level according to the current objective trends of self-government development and impose at the same time new obligations on regional policy.

Public administration of the region as an integrated economy, ensuring the integrated development of the region is a relatively new task. It is worth noting that until now the territorial administration did not have sufficient autonomy, and was often limited to the local economy only. In the current conditions of decentralization of power in Ukraine, when the regional entities of our state have greater autonomy, it is necessary to develop a concept of a system of regional governance for a particular model of market relations, taking into account the experience of other countries [4].

Human resources management of the region is a subsystem in the general system of public administration of all spheres of life of the population. If we consider the region as an object of human resource management, it can be represented as a system of interdependent subsystems of activity of the population living on its territory requiring clear managerial impact. Each of these subsystems has its characteristics which determine the way to be managed in the region. Moreover, the activities of the administrative bodies of the executive power should be aimed at creating decent

20 November 2020

conditions of life of the population and solving all problems of the reproductive cycle: formation, distribution, redistribution and use of human resources.

Meanwhile, regions are aimed at managing the development of public production, market environment, science and education, health care, providing employment for the population and meeting the needs of the state economy in skilled personnel. These processes are relatively independent, and they determine the boundaries of the object of talent management [5, p. 188]. The diversity of the object and the socio-economic functions of managing this talent results in the specificity of the management entities.

What is specific about the public administration objects is that their layers exist at all levels of government, from the region to the enterprise. Thus, the regional and municipal administration tackles in the territory under its jurisdiction all issues on the management of labor potential and human resources, exercises control over work in this area. Besides, it is at the regional economy level that a complete cycle of reproduction in its phases is provided. In particular, within the oblast as a territorial unit full reproduction of human resources, including engineering and scientific personnel is possible. For the integrated management of workforce circulation, it is necessary to develop a system that operationally carries out this task at the national and regional levels. In our opinion, to ensure the effective functioning of the regional labor market in Ukraine it is necessary to find a conceptual and functional balance in the work of the above-mentioned bodies.

The key elements of the regional personnel policy based on this model can be worded as follows [6, p.299]:

- ensuring a socially acceptable level of employment;
- facilitating the flow of labor to the economic sector, territory and types of employment in the interests of structural shifts in industry, region and productivity growth;
- maintaining and developing a skilled core of human resources when dealing with over-staffing;
- social support for the unemployed.

The proposed model should be aimed at solving the following problems:

- support for the employment of the skilled part of the human resources of industrial enterprises and the potential of the employed population in the activities related to scientific and technological progress and use of advanced technologies which are temporarily in crisis;
- support for retraining of qualified personnel, the need for which is reduced as a result of expected structural changes in the modernization or due to bankruptcy;
- promoting the fastest employment of unemployed skilled personnel to prevent loss of qualifications;
- compulsory vocational school graduates' job market entry if their specialty meets the demand of the economy, or first-in-time (in comparison with other population) training taking into account the situation on the labor market;
- promoting the restoration of human resources to increase skilled and economically mobile human resources in promising enterprises that have lost a large number of qualified employees due to the decline in production and low pay;
- curbing hidden unemployment growth;
- promoting employment;
- regulation of the territorial rates and magnitude of bankruptcies of enterprises, taking into account situations at specific enterprises, to prevent a catastrophic rise in unemployment and transition to long-term unemployment;

20 November 2020

- assisting low-skilled or unprofessional unemployed in finding employment;

The Employment Service of Ukraine is the central body of executive power, which oversees the work on ensuring the state employment policy. According to the author, this narrows the functions of the employment centers. After all, the main disadvantage of these centers, as shown by the analysis, is that they only deal with the working-age population, who is currently unemployed. These centers coordinate the activities of the regional labor market only indirectly [7]. It would, therefore, be even better to delineate the functions of personnel policy formation between the two institutions:

- the Department of State Employment Service (subordinate to the state);
- regional labor committee (subordinate to the region).

It is advisable to delineate the functions between two structures at the city level: the city employment committee (department) and the training center.

The main activities of such employment centers can be as follows:

- ensuring social protection for the unemployed;
- promoting the vocational training and retraining of workers who have lost their jobs and certain categories of unemployed,
- forecasting the number of unemployed by categories;
- interaction with state social security bodies, executive authorities, local self-government on employment issues;
- information, consulting and educational work;
- formation of a legal framework;
- marketing of employment services;
- cooperation with employers (control of compliance with employment legislation; support of job-saving and creating enterprises; retraining of workers to be dismissed) [8, p. 305].

In addition to public employment services, private enterprises that are focused on recruiting temporary workers, highly skilled specialists, assisting in the structural restructuring of enterprises and organizations should function in the labor market.

In our view, the prerequisites for creating such a vertical interaction are:

- the need to create a theoretical concept of functioning and development prospects (at the state and regional level) of the structures that determine the personnel policy of the city and the organization;
- lack of bodies coordinating the activities of the state, local and business structures, educational centers;
- lack of support of scientific base and legal regulation of personnel work;
- the process of formation of managerial and entrepreneurial culture;
- lack of a clear, logical scheme of training and retraining of human resources;
- the need for a strategic approach, full inclusion, and funding of training, retraining and career planning programs;
- inconsistency of demand forecasting programs for specialists in specific specialties.

The development of a new model for the implementation of personnel policy of the regional socio-economic system can increase investment attractiveness of the region and the city. For that purpose, the proposed project must be implemented in coordination with other programs, first of all, with the programs of reforming, restructuring large and medium-sized enterprises, saving and creating new jobs [9, p. 79].

The second area of public administration in the formation of personnel policy of the region is the development of a system of training. However, it should be borne in mind that training alone cannot increase employment. It leads to an increase in the quality of labor resources, which in turn contributes to the increase of labor productivity, the

20 November 2020

acceleration of scientific and technological progress and the rate of growth of production. And as a consequence, expanded reproduction can lead to an increase in jobs, that is, employment growth. Therefore, the result of upgrading personnel skill level can only be seen after a certain period.

3 Conclusions from the conducted research

Adequate governance mechanism is needed to realize the goals of the long-term employment policy of the state human resources. The complex nature of personnel policy measures in Ukraine necessitates the formation of an information-coordinating structure that will be able to take on the functions of information and coordinating development of the personnel structures of the state and individual regions in managing the processes of reproduction of human resources.

The improvement of the organizational arrangement of public administration in the formation of personnel policy of the region should be based on the world experience of economically developed countries and include professional training and retraining, vocational training and stimulation of adaptation to the situation on the labor market, encouraging the unemployed to actively search for work, and entrepreneurs to increase employment providing them with subsidies and tax benefits, creating favorable conditions for entrepreneurs to hire certain groups of unemployed (young people, people with disabilities, long-term unemployed). Furthermore, the system of training should also develop actively, with further full employment of the trained in the areas of acquired knowledge and skills.

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